

Elastic anisotropy in additive-manufactured titanium alloys studied by resonant ultrasound spectroscopy

Martin Koller¹, Michaela Janovská¹, Petr Sedlák¹, Hanuš Seiner¹

¹ Institute of Thermomechanics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Dolejškova 1402/5, 182 00 Praha 8, Czechia

koller@it.cas.cz ¹

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Titanium alloys offer a remarkable combination of high strength and toughness, along with excellent fatigue and corrosion resistance, while maintaining low density and low elastic moduli. Their favourable strength-to-density ratio makes them attractive for a wide range of industrial applications, whereas the combination of low elastic modulus and biocompatibility is particularly promising for biomedical uses, such as hip implants. Among Ti alloys, metastable alloys exhibit the lowest elastic moduli, while possessing complex multiphase microstructures comprising α , β or ω -Ti phases. The phase composition and the resulting elastic properties are strongly influenced by various alloying elements, where even minor variations in elemental combinations can lead to significant changes in alloy properties. Additive manufacturing (AM) is particularly advantageous in this context, as it enables the fabrication of a wide variety of alloy compositions directly from elemental powders.

In this study, the elastic properties of various additively manufactured titanium alloys were investigated by laser-based resonant ultrasound spectroscopy (RUS) [1]. This technique allows determination of the complete set of elastic coefficients from the resonant spectrum of a freely vibrating millimetre-sized sample. The investigated materials included pure α -Ti, an $\alpha+\beta$ Ti6Al4V alloy, and TiNb-based β -Ti alloys fabricated by different AM techniques, namely cold spraying, directed energy deposition, and laser powder bed fusion. As the AM processing often induces a substantial crystallographic texture, particular attention was paid to its influence on the elastic anisotropy.

Figure 1a) shows an example of a resonant spectrum of a Ti30Nb1Fe2Sn sample, fabricated using powder bed fusion via laser beam (PBF-LB) at the Department of Manufacturing and Materials Engineering, School of Mechanical Engineering, University of Campinas, Brazil [2]. Figure 1b) shows three of the associated resonant frequencies and their modal shapes of vibration (i. e. the out-of-plane displacements at the measured face of the sample). This sample exhibits transverse isotropy: its elastic properties were found to be the same within the horizontal plane (within experimental uncertainty), but they significantly differ along the build direction. Figure 1c) shows the angular distribution of Young's modulus as a function of the angle from the horizontal plane (the build direction thus corresponds to 90° in this polar plot). Young's modulus in the horizontal plane was determined to be 70.8 GPa (with experimental uncertainty of ± 1.5 GPa), whereas the build direction shows the highest value of 78.7 GPa. Nevertheless, the lowest Young's modulus of 60.4 GPa was found in the direction close to the 45° angle, implying that the diagonal directions in these AM β -Ti alloys are the elastically softest. A clear correlation between crystallographic texture and elastic anisotropy was observed in the investigated AM Ti alloys.

Figure 1 a) Resonant spectrum of Ti30Nb1Fe2Sn sample, b) examples of resonant frequencies used for RUS determination of elastic properties, c) angular distribution of Young's modulus as a function of the angle from the horizontal plane.

For the biomedical use, the presence of crystallographic texture can be beneficial, as it would enable the directions with the lowest Young's modulus to be aligned with the principal loading direction of the implants, which would limit the stress shielding caused by mismatch of elastic properties between the bone and the implant.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Ferrous Multifunctionalities project no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004591, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic, co-funded by the European Union, and by the Czech Science Foundation project no. GC24-11074].

REFERENCES

- [1] Petr Sedlák, Hanuš Seiner, Jan Zídek, Michaela Janovská, Michal Landa. Determination of All 21 Independent Elastic Coefficients of Generally Anisotropic Solids by Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy: Benchmark Examples. *Experimental Mechanics* 54 (2014) 1073 - 1085, doi:10.1007/s11340-014-9862-6
- [2] Kristína Bartha, Michaela Šlapáková, Kateřina Ficková, Dalibor Preisler, Jiří Kozlík, Martin Koller, Lucie Bodnárová, João Felipe Queiroz Rodrigues, Márcio Sangali, Matheus Valentim, Rubens Caram, Josef Stráský, Miloš Janeček. Additive manufacturing of metastable beta Ti–Nb–Fe–Sn alloys with tuned mechanical properties for biomedical implants: Processing–structure–property relationships and alloy selection for implant design. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 39 (2025) 7357-7368, doi:10.1016/j.jmrt.2025.11.064.